

WAYS TO IMPROVE MANAGEMENT ACTIVITIES IN THE HOTEL BUSINESS

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Abstract. *In this article, the evaluation of tourist attractions, existing and planned tourist facilities and services and their improvement, organization of tours and trips, means of accommodation, recommended volumes and forms of tourism are considered.*

Keywords: *Hotel, tourist facility, service, plan, program, complex, infrastructure, analysis.*

ПУТИ СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЯ УПРАВЛЕНЧЕСКОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ В ГОСТИНИЧНОМ БИЗНЕСЕ

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассмотрены оценка туристических достопримечательностей, существующих и планируемых туристических объектов и услуг и их усовершенствование, организация туров и поездок, средства размещения, рекомендуемые объемы и формы туризма.*

Ключевые слова: *Гостиница, туристический объект, сервис, план, программа, комплекс, инфраструктура, анализ.*

The development of tourism is directly related to the improvement of the efficiency and quality of the sectors related to this complex, including the hotel industry. Despite having rich tourist resources, the level of utilization of the available opportunities in Uzbekistan is much lower than required. With the expansion of the scale of tourism, the number of service enterprises, including hotels, continues to increase.

In the development of plans and programs, it is necessary to apply the principles of rational planning first. They provide great economic benefits without any environmental or social problems. It is necessary to pay special attention to the complex approach. It envisages the balance of economic, ecological, social and cultural aspects and ensures the sustainable development of tourism at all stages.

Comprehensive plans and recommendations must include many interrelated, diverse elements. The main ones are:

- economic, ecological, social, cultural and other goals and directions of tourism development;
- general basic analysis - obtaining historical information about the country, the region, their brief geographical description, susceptibility to natural disasters (volcanoes, earthquakes, hurricanes, etc.), climatic conditions, quality of the environment, general development plans and programs of the region, and their impact on tourism, demographic, cultural models, models of existing sectors in the economy and their development trends (income of the population, its employment, etc.);
- analysis and recommendations in terms of infrastructure - access to the region or country by various means of transport, transfer potential and facilities for tourists; sewerage, telecommunications in tourist areas; existing and ongoing plans and programs for infrastructure

improvement; infrastructure factors that hinder the development of tourism, recommendations for infrastructure improvement;

- tourist attractions, types of activities for their improvement - researching existing potential attractions and preparing a list of them by category (natural, cultural, etc.); their evaluation in terms of the use of attractions; recommendations and measures for their preservation; significant positive and negative factors (political instability, natural disasters, crime, etc.);

- evaluation of existing and planned tourist facilities and services and their improvement - recommendations for organizing tours and trips, accommodation facilities, restaurants, banks, currency exchange offices, stores;

- recommended volumes and forms of tourism - to determine the potential of tourism within the country or region (district), taking into account the satisfaction of tourists, justifying the most appropriate forms, volumes and scope of tourism;

- market analysis and forecasting - global, international, regional and local models; patterns and trends of tourist arrivals; general characteristics of tourists coming to this country or region; the impact of competing tourist facilities; local residents' use of tourist attractions, facilities and services; predict placement tools to achieve market objectives;

- recommended tourism development and structural plan - a strategic guideline covering economic, ecological and socio-cultural factors; types and locations of tourist attractions; tourism development districts (tourist zones) and transport links; construction stages by terms; models and programs of tours showing tourist-excursion routes;

- economic analysis and recommendations - current and forecasted volume and types of tourism expenditures; predicted impact of tourism on the economy of the country (region), income in foreign currency; revenues received; population employment; share added to state revenues; recommendations for strengthening the economic benefits of tourism at the local, regional and national levels;

- environmental aspects and recommendations - existing environmental problems related to tourism and recommendations for their mitigation; in the future, measures to eliminate negative environmental consequences and strengthen positive effects, to strengthen the general ecological quality of tourist districts, to select the necessary directions of policies and programs in the field of environmental protection, preservation of ecological heritage; environmental impact assessment of specific tourism projects;

- socio-cultural aspects and recommendations - positive and negative socio-cultural effects caused by tourism; alleviating negative effects and strengthening positive ones; tourism education programs, informational materials on explaining local cultural traditions and rules of conduct to tourists; local population participation in all aspects of tourism;

- institutional aspects and recommendations - evaluation of mutual cooperation of state, commercial and private structures in the field of tourism, making changes to existing structures or creating new ones for effective management of tourism and coordination of activities between state agencies, public sector and private sector; to evaluate the current laws and regulations in the field of tourism, to make changes to the current recommendations or to adopt new ones; assessment of financial and human resources for investment in the tourism sector; educational and vocational training programs, etc.

An important aspect of the planning process is the determination of strategies and methods of implementation of the plan's recommendations. For this, it is necessary to develop ways and methods of its implementation in advance. Recently, special explanatory documents are becoming more and more widespread. It is a guideline for consistency in the implementation of the plan.

After comprehensive consideration and agreement of the project at the appropriate level (government, regional and local authorities, firm), the final version of the plan is adopted and its financial basis is established. Changes may be made during execution.

An integral part of the implementation of the plan is to control its implementation in the following directions: the number and nature of tourist arrivals; satisfaction level of tourists; economic, ecological and socio-cultural impact of tourism both in general and in relation to specific specific projects.

It is important to strictly adhere to the deadlines for the planned activities. It is appropriate to use mathematical methods and computer technology. Continuous management should never be forgotten. It covers:

- adapting to changing market trends and product evolution;
- support and improve the quality of facilities and services;
- continuously increase the social and geographical benefits of tourism;
- solving problems as they arise, etc.

Thus, for the sustainable development of tourism, it is necessary to carry out the activities developed in the plans and to effectively manage this process.

The tourism industry has been recognized as the largest, most profitable and fastest growing industry for many years. Today, Uzbekistan is trying to take its rightful place in the world tourism market. According to the results of 2021, the number of tourists who came to our country for the first time will reach 1 million. exceeded a person. Although the share of the tourism sector in the gross domestic product of our country increased from 0.6% to 1.5% in 2021 compared to 2020, it cannot fully express its current potential. Nevertheless, the number of visiting tourists is growing year by year.

Samarkand region is one of the most attractive tourist regions in our country. According to the information of the General Directorate for Protection and Use of Cultural Heritage Objects of the Republic, 806 architectural monuments, 25 places of particular interest, and more than 100 monumental art objects have been registered with the state. Monuments of historical cities of Samarkand, Kattakogan, old streets, ancient architectural monuments of Pakhtachi, Okdarya, Nurabad, Urgut and other districts - mosques and madrasas, archaeological monuments, etc. In 2021, 25,523 people were served by 44 tourist service enterprises in Samarkand region, 14,676 of them were foreign tourists.

According to the above table, the number of tourists received in 2021 was 20,665 more than the number of tourists sent to foreign countries. When we analyze the reasons for this, we see that regional tourism products are not designed to keep tourists for more than 3 days. The tours are organized in such a way that most tourists spend 1 night in the city of Samarkand and return the next day. For example, 214,201 people visited Samarkand region last year, but only 129,271 people (60%) stayed in hotels. 115,426 or 89% of inpatients stay for 1-3 days. The seasonality and unevenness of the flow of tourists during the week also have a negative impact on the results.

To improve the situation, first of all, it is necessary to focus on solving the following tasks:

- activation of mutual cooperation of the central and local executive bodies, as well as the state and private sector in issues of tourism infrastructure development;
- introduction of effective forms of tourism management;
- improving the system of statistical calculations and reports for monitoring the dynamics of the sector, developing scientifically based forecasts;
- to raise the quality of tourist and hotel services to international standards;
- creation and improvement of specialized tourist zones.

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